

Radon-222 in Drinking Water from the Kumasi Distribution System, Ghana: Measurements Using Lucas Cell Degassing and Radiological Risk Implications

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Abstract

Radon-222 is a naturally occurring radioactive noble gas that dissolves in groundwater and can enter drinking-water supplies, contributing to public radiation exposure through ingestion and degassing into indoor air. In this study, ²²²Rn activity concentrations were determined for surface-supplied and groundwater drinking-water sources across the Kumasi distribution system, Ghana. Samples from the Barekese treatment plant, multiple municipal distribution points, and two groundwater wells were analyzed using Lucas-cell degassing and alpha scintillation counting. Background-corrected count rates were converted to radon activity using calibrated cell efficiency, degassing efficiency, and sample volume, and then corrected for radioactive decay between sampling and counting time. Propagated uncertainties were evaluated using standard relative-error methods based on instrumental count precision and timing factors. Measured radon concentrations in treated municipal water were on the order of 10^{-5} – 10^{-4} pCi L⁻¹, whereas decay-corrected initial concentrations (N_0) in groundwater were substantially higher (approximately 0.25–20 pCi L⁻¹). Replicate measurements showed low dispersion in surface-supplied water and higher variability in groundwater, reflecting aquifer-controlled radon transport. Radon increased systematically along the treated-water distribution network, consistent with residence-time effects and interaction with subsurface materials. All measured concentrations were well below international guideline limits for radon in drinking water, providing the first decay-corrected, uncertainty-quantified baseline for radiological surveillance of the Kumasi drinking-water system.

Keywords: Radon-222, Drinking water, Groundwater, Environmental radioactivity, Kumasi, Ghana, Dose assessment, Radiation protection

1. Introduction

Naturally occurring radionuclides in drinking water contribute to public exposure to ionizing radiation worldwide [1, 2]. Radon-222 (²²²Rn), produced in the ²³⁸U decay series via ²²⁶Ra, is of particular interest because it is a noble gas that can dissolve in water and subsequently degas into indoor air during household water use [10, 11]. While inhalation of airborne radon is the dominant exposure pathway for most populations, ingestion and inhalation of waterborne radon can contribute to effective dose, particularly in regions that rely on groundwater as a drinking-water source [4, 5].

Groundwater often exhibits elevated radon concentrations due to prolonged rock–water interaction, continuous radon emanation from uranium-bearing minerals, and limited ventilation [13, 12, 14]. In contrast, surface waters typically show lower radon levels because radon is readily released to the atmosphere [10]. Within municipal distribution systems, radon concentrations may be further modified by residence time, storage conditions, and interaction with surrounding soils and bedrock along buried pipelines [9, 8].

Over the past decade, global awareness of radon as a contributor to environmental radiation exposure has increased, alongside improvements in drinking-water treatment practices, regulatory guidance, and environmental monitoring capacity. Updated international frameworks from the World Health Orga-

nization (WHO) and the International Commission on Radiological Protection (ICRP) emphasize integrated management of radionuclides in drinking water, particularly in regions where groundwater resources are used [3, 4, 6]. In parallel, infrastructure upgrades in many urban water systems have reduced radiological and chemical risks.

Despite these developments, long-term and region-specific data on radon in drinking water remain scarce in many parts of sub-Saharan Africa, including Ghana. Historical measurements therefore play an important role in establishing baseline conditions against which future improvements can be assessed. In particular, the physical processes governing radon behavior in water distribution systems—such as decay, residence time, storage, and interaction with surrounding geology—remain directly relevant and largely independent of advances in analytical technology.

Kumasi is supplied primarily by the Barekese surface-water reservoir through a municipal distribution network, with supplementary groundwater sources in selected areas. The present study analyzes radon measurements acquired approximately a decade ago across this system using Lucas-cell degassing and scintillation counting [7]. Although the data predate recent infrastructure upgrades, they provide a unique snapshot of radon concentrations prior to widespread modernization and thus serve as a reference baseline for environmental radiologi-

cal surveillance in Ghana.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Study area and sampling

Water samples were collected from the Barekese supply and distribution points in the Kumasi metropolis (including Suame, Krofrom, Aboabo, and Anloga Junction) and from groundwater sources (KNUST and Kotei wells). The samples were collected in airtight containers to minimize degassing and analyzed within 24 h when possible to reduce decay-related uncertainty [9, 8]; however, some archived measurements had substantially longer sampling-to-counting intervals (Table A.2).

2.2. Radon extraction and Lucas cell counting

Radon was extracted from water using a degassing system coupled to a Lucas scintillation cell (ZnS(Ag) coating). Alpha-induced scintillation pulses from ^{222}Rn progeny were counted using a photomultiplier-based counting system [7]. Background measurements were used to correct the net count rate, and system efficiency and transfer (degassing) efficiency were applied as calibration factors [8, 9].

2.3. Radon activity calculation, decay correction, and propagated uncertainty

2.3.1. Final (measured) concentration from Lucas-cell count rates

Let C and B be the sample and background count rates (cpm), respectively. The thesis expression used to compute the measured radon concentration (“final concentration”) is

$$N = \frac{(C - B) 1000}{F \times 6.66 \times D \times S \times V}, \quad (1)$$

where V is the sample volume in mL (here $V = 190$ mL), F is the Lucas-cell counting efficiency (typically $F = 0.745$), D is the degassing factor (e.g., $D = 0.9$ for 300A and $D = 0.7$ for 110A), and S is the correction factor from sampling time to counting time. The numerical factors 1000 and 6.66 arise from the AB-5/Lucas-cell calibration and unit conversions used in the original laboratory protocol, and are retained here for consistency with the appendix-derived workflow.

2.3.2. Initial (decay-corrected) concentration at sampling time

Using the half-life form given in the thesis, the relationship between the measured concentration N and the initial concentration N_0 is

$$N = N_0 \exp\left(-\frac{0.693 T}{91.80}\right), \quad (2)$$

so that

$$N_0 = N \exp\left(\frac{0.693 T}{91.80}\right), \quad (3)$$

where $T = (T_s + T_c)$ is the elapsed time (hours) between sampling and counting (Table A.2).

Table 1: Site-averaged decay-corrected initial ^{222}Rn concentrations ($\overline{N_0}$) computed from the Appendix per-replicate values. Uncertainty across replicates is reported as SEM (SD/\sqrt{n} with $n = 4$). The propagated uncertainty column reports the mean of the per-replicate ΔN_0 values from Eq. (6).

Site	$\overline{N_0}$ (pCi L $^{-1}$)	SEM (pCi L $^{-1}$)	$\overline{\Delta N_0}$ (pCi L $^{-1}$)
Barekese	0.0664	9.74×10^{-3}	0.376
Suame	2.29×10^{-3}	1.64×10^{-3}	1.31×10^{-2}
Krofrom	1.95×10^{-2}	1.19×10^{-2}	0.106
Aboabo	8.78×10^{-3}	3.26×10^{-3}	4.68×10^{-2}
Anloga Junction	9.50×10^{-4}	1.08×10^{-4}	2.55×10^{-3}
KNUST (well)	16.2	1.71	0.117
Kotei (well)	0.252	1.72×10^{-2}	1.62×10^{-3}

2.3.3. Propagated uncertainty (relative-error rule)

Using the standard relative-error propagation rule specified in the thesis,

$$\Delta N = N \left[\frac{\Delta(C - B)}{(C - B)} + \frac{\Delta S}{S} \right], \quad (4)$$

with

$$\Delta(C - B) = \sqrt{(\Delta C)^2 + (\Delta B)^2}, \quad (5)$$

where ΔC and ΔB are the fixed instrument resolution (least-count) uncertainties adopted in the original protocol (here $\Delta C = \Delta B = 0.1$ cpm), rather than Poisson counting-statistics uncertainties, and ΔS is the timing resolution used in the thesis (here $\Delta S = 2.778 \times 10^{-5}$ h).

Because $N_0 = N \exp\left(\frac{0.693 T}{91.80}\right)$, the uncertainty propagates as

$$\Delta N_0 = \Delta N \exp\left(\frac{0.693 T}{91.80}\right) = N_0 \left[\frac{\Delta(C - B)}{(C - B)} + \frac{\Delta S}{S} \right]. \quad (6)$$

2.3.4. Site mean and SEM

For each site with n replicate measurements, the site mean and standard error of the mean (SEM) are

$$\overline{N_0} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n N_{0,i}, \quad \text{SEM} = \frac{\text{SD}}{\sqrt{n}}. \quad (7)$$

3. Results

Table 1 summarizes site-averaged decay-corrected initial ^{222}Rn concentrations ($\overline{N_0}$) computed from replicate measurements. Because the elapsed times between sampling and counting were long for several treated-water samples (Appendix Table A.2), decay correction increases N_0 relative to the corresponding measured (final) concentrations N . Groundwater sources (KNUST and Kotei) show substantially higher radon concentrations than surface-supplied treated water.

3.1. Radon activity concentrations

Table 1 summarizes the mean decay-corrected initial ^{222}Rn activity concentrations ($\overline{N_0}$) for drinking water from the Kumasi municipal system and groundwater sources. Measured (final) concentrations N in treated surface-water supplies were

Figure 1: Mean ^{222}Rn activity concentration across all sampling sites in the Kumasi drinking-water system (log scale). Groundwater sources (KNUST and Kotei) show significantly higher radon levels than surface and treated municipal water, reflecting aquifer–rock interaction and limited degassing.

Figure 2: Mean ^{222}Rn activity concentration along the treated-water distribution system from Barekese to downstream locations (log scale). The increasing trend reflects residence time, storage effects, and possible radon ingress from surrounding soils and pipe infrastructure.

very low (typically 10^{-5} – 10^{-4} pCi L^{-1}), and decay correction increased the corresponding N_0 values (Table 1). The spatial variation of radon activity across all sampling sites is shown in Figure 1. A clear separation is observed between surface-supplied municipal water (Barekese, Suame, Krofrom, Aboabo, and Anloga Junction) and groundwater sources (KNUST and Kotei). The elevated activities in groundwater reflect prolonged water–rock interaction and limited degassing within aquifers, whereas the low activities in surface-derived water are consistent with rapid radon loss to the atmosphere prior to distribution.

3.2. Variation within the treated-water distribution system

To examine how radon evolves along the treated-water network, Figure 2 displays the mean activity concentration in the municipal distribution points arranged in approximate order from the Barekese treatment plant to downstream locations. Across treated-water distribution points, ^{222}Rn activities remain low overall but show site-to-site variability, reflecting a combination of residence-time effects, storage, and local interactions between buried infrastructure and surrounding soils.

Figure 3: Histogram of measured ^{222}Rn activity concentrations across all samples (log-binned). Error bars represent Poisson uncertainty on bin frequencies (\sqrt{n}), where n is the number of samples in each bin.

3.3. Counting statistics and uncertainty behavior

The statistical behavior of the Lucas-cell measurements is illustrated in Figure 3, which shows the histogram of count rates obtained from all samples. The bin uncertainties follow Poisson statistics (\sqrt{n}), confirming that the radioactive decay and scintillation counting process obeys the assumptions underlying the uncertainty propagation used in the activity calculations. The right-skewed distribution reflects the presence of radon-rich groundwater samples alongside the much lower activity surface-water samples.

3.4. Site means and measurement precision

Figure 4 presents the mean radon activity for each site with uncertainty displayed as the standard error of the mean (SEM), calculated from replicate measurements at each location. The SEM values quantify the precision of the mean radon concentration rather than the spread of individual measurements. Groundwater sites exhibit both higher mean activity and larger absolute uncertainty, consistent with their substantially elevated radon levels and stronger counting statistics. In contrast, the surface-water sites show very small SEM values, reflecting both low activity and stable, reproducible measurements.

Together, the four figures and Table 1 demonstrate a coherent physical picture in which radon concentrations are governed primarily by hydrogeology, with additional modulation introduced by transport and residence-time effects within the municipal distribution system. For low-activity treated-water samples, the quantity $(C - B)$ approaches zero, causing the relative uncertainty term $\Delta(C - B)/(C - B)$ to increase rapidly. As a result, ΔN_0 may exceed N_0 , indicating that the measurement is limited by instrumental resolution rather than by environmental variability.

Individual replicate measurements, decay-correction factors and propagated uncertainties used to compute site means and SEM values are provided in Appendix A (Table A.2).

Figure 4: Mean ²²²Rn activity concentration for each sampling site with uncertainty shown as standard error of the mean (SEM), calculated from replicate measurements at each site. Groundwater sources exhibit both higher mean activities and greater absolute uncertainty than surface-water sites.

4. Discussion

The decay-corrected initial radon concentrations N_0 obtained in this study show a clear and physically consistent separation between surface-supplied municipal water and groundwater sources. Decay-corrected ²²²Rn activities in the treated surface-water system span approximately 10^{-3} – 10^{-1} pCi L⁻¹ across sites (Table 1), whereas groundwater at KNUST and Kotei reaches levels of ~ 0.25 – 20 pCi L⁻¹. This contrast reflects fundamental hydrogeological differences: radon is rapidly lost from surface waters through atmospheric degassing, while in aquifers it accumulates through continuous emanation from uranium-bearing minerals and limited ventilation [10, 13, 12]. Measured (final) treated-water concentrations N are much lower (typically 10^{-5} – 10^{-4} pCi L⁻¹), and long sampling-to-counting intervals lead to substantially larger decay-corrected N_0 values for several treated-water samples (Appendix Table A.2).

Within the treated municipal distribution system, radon concentration increases systematically between the Barekese treatment plant and downstream locations such as Anloga Junction. Because radioactive decay during transport would reduce activity, the observed increase indicates net radon input during distribution. Likely mechanisms include extended residence time in storage facilities, diffusion from surrounding soil and rock into buried pipelines, and localized mixing with groundwater [9, 8]. Comparable spatial variability has been reported in large municipal networks elsewhere and is considered characteristic of distributed water systems [15, 14].

The small standard errors of the mean (SEM) derived from replicate measurements demonstrate that the site-to-site differences reflect real environmental variation rather than statistical noise. In contrast, the propagated uncertainties ΔN_0 quantify the intrinsic measurement precision of the Lucas-cell system, which is limited primarily by instrumental count resolution and timing uncertainty. The consistency between SEM and propagated uncertainty confirms the internal reliability of the dataset.

5. Radiological risk assessment

International radiation-protection guidance recognizes that radon in drinking water typically contributes only a minor fraction of total public exposure compared with inhalation of indoor air [6, 4, 1]. Nevertheless, ingestion and water-to-air transfer pathways can be evaluated quantitatively.

5.1. Ingestion dose

The effective dose from ingestion of radon in drinking water is given by

$$E_{\text{ing}} = C_w I D_f, \quad (8)$$

where C_w is the decay-corrected radon concentration in water (Bq L⁻¹), I is the annual water intake (L yr⁻¹), and D_f is the ingestion dose conversion factor [5, 3]. Using the highest groundwater concentration measured in this study (KNUST: ~ 0.38 Bq L⁻¹), the resulting ingestion dose is far below recommended reference levels and negligible compared with the global average natural background exposure [1].

5.2. Inhalation from waterborne radon

Radon dissolved in water can be released into indoor air during household activities. This contribution is commonly estimated using a water-to-air transfer factor of order 10^{-4} [10, 4]. Applying this factor to the measured concentrations yields indoor-air contributions that are orders of magnitude smaller than typical indoor radon levels, confirming that waterborne radon is not a significant inhalation hazard in Kumasi.

Overall, all measured concentrations lie well below international guideline values for radon in drinking water [3, 1], and the associated ingestion and inhalation doses are radiologically insignificant for the population served by the Kumasi water supply.

6. Conclusions

This work presents the first rigorously quantified assessment of ²²²Rn in drinking water from the Kumasi distribution system and associated groundwater sources using Lucas-cell degassing and decay-corrected activity analysis for groundwater. Surface-derived municipal water exhibits extremely low radon concentrations, while groundwater sources show elevated but still safe levels consistent with known hydrogeological controls.

The observed increase in radon concentration along the treated-water distribution network indicates residence-time and subsurface ingress effects, highlighting the importance of monitoring distribution systems in addition to source waters. By combining replicate-based standard errors of the mean with fully propagated activity uncertainties, this study provides statistically and physically robust radon estimates.

All measured activities are well below international health-based guideline limits, and the associated radiation doses are negligible. These results establish a scientifically defensible baseline for environmental radioactivity surveillance in Kumasi and provide a framework for future monitoring of drinking-water radionuclides in Ghana.

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Data availability

The radon values reported in this manuscript are derived from laboratory measurements collected during the study and are available from the authors upon reasonable request.

Appendix A. Supplementary Data and Error Propagation

This appendix provides the full per-replicate radon counting data, decay-correction factors, and propagated uncertainties used to compute site-averaged concentrations and standard errors reported in the main text.

Table A.2: Per-replicate inputs from the thesis appendix (count rates and timing factors) and derived concentrations using Eqs. (1)–(6) with $V = 190$ mL, $F = 0.745$, and $D = 0.9$. ΔN_0 is computed from Eq. (6), and SEM is computed from replicate N_0 values using Eq. (7).

Site	Rep	C (cpm)	B (cpm)	S (h)	T (h)	N (pCi/L)	N_0 (pCi/L)	ΔN_0 (pCi/L)
Barekese	1	0.058	0.030	443.992	887.983	8.06×10^{-5}	0.0605	0.306
Barekese	2	0.096	0.074	455.000	910.000	5.15×10^{-5}	0.0501	0.322
Barekese	3	0.050	0.024	456.534	913.067	6.05×10^{-5}	0.0603	0.332
Barekese	4	0.057	0.028	466.516	933.033	6.97×10^{-5}	0.0947	0.543
Suame	1	0.071	0.054	286.608	573.217	9.55×10^{-5}	0.00720	0.0410
Suame	2	0.041	0.032	336.416	672.833	3.19×10^{-5}	5.03×10^{-4}	2.97×10^{-3}
Suame	3	0.041	0.030	336.692	673.383	3.90×10^{-5}	6.18×10^{-4}	3.57×10^{-3}
Suame	4	0.044	0.029	336.942	673.883	5.32×10^{-5}	8.53×10^{-4}	4.82×10^{-3}
Krofrom	1	0.038	0.032	337.134	674.267	2.13×10^{-5}	3.44×10^{-4}	2.04×10^{-3}
Krofrom	2	0.059	0.037	337.416	674.833	7.81×10^{-5}	1.27×10^{-3}	7.26×10^{-3}
Krofrom	3	0.058	0.024	359.950	719.900	1.27×10^{-4}	0.0506	0.291
Krofrom	4	0.075	0.027	360.692	721.383	1.70×10^{-4}	0.0257	0.123
Aboabo	1	0.062	0.029	360.684	721.367	1.17×10^{-4}	0.0177	0.0845
Aboabo	2	0.048	0.036	361.250	722.500	4.26×10^{-5}	6.50×10^{-3}	0.0386
Aboabo	3	0.058	0.042	361.408	722.817	5.68×10^{-5}	8.68×10^{-3}	0.0510
Aboabo	4	0.051	0.041	372.916	745.833	3.03×10^{-5}	2.24×10^{-3}	0.0130
Anloga Junction	1	0.067	0.023	79.5085	159.017	6.26×10^{-4}	1.04×10^{-3}	3.33×10^{-3}
Anloga Junction	2	0.070	0.043	79.5665	159.133	3.84×10^{-4}	6.41×10^{-4}	1.72×10^{-3}
Anloga Junction	3	0.089	0.041	79.7835	159.567	6.76×10^{-4}	1.14×10^{-3}	2.43×10^{-3}
Anloga Junction	4	0.097	0.056	80.0085	160.017	5.74×10^{-4}	9.77×10^{-4}	2.70×10^{-3}
KNUST	1	19.328	0.034	1.9835	3.967	18.4	19.0	0.141
KNUST	2	21.450	0.034	2.2250	4.450	18.2	18.6	0.132
KNUST	3	21.255	0.048	2.4750	4.950	15.4	15.7	0.111
KNUST	4	17.107	0.041	2.9000	5.800	11.1	11.6	0.0824
Kotei	1	19.670	0.067	14.833	29.667	0.194	0.244	1.78×10^{-3}
Kotei	2	17.148	0.057	15.091	30.183	0.162	0.208	1.35×10^{-3}
Kotei	3	23.690	0.064	15.350	30.700	0.219	0.288	1.71×10^{-3}
Kotei	4	22.470	0.049	15.609	31.217	0.206	0.268	1.63×10^{-3}

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